

High-Fidelity Neutronics/CFD coupling for a LW-SMR Steam Line Break transient analysis

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ABSTRACT

As part of the development of High-Fidelity calculation schemes at Framatome to support Industrial code validation and margin quantification in performance and safety studies, a first coupling of the COCAGNE SPn core solver co-developed between Framatome and EdF in the frame of the ODYSSEE platform, and the ANSYS Fluent CFD code has been implemented and tested on a small LWR based on the KAIST-1A core. Both codes were fully validated separately but never coupled before this benchmark. The core and its primary system were modeled in simplified transport/CFD (SAS model in the lower plenum, porous approximation in the core). After first test on the numerical stability of the coupling in stationary mode, a Steam Line Break transient is performed with given hypotheses. The paper describes the first results for a 10 second transient, pointing out the strong impact of turbulence and fluid redistribution on the 3D power variations. The findings of this study show that the coupled CFD/neutronic approach is capable of accurately predict both steady-state and transient behaviors, including complex redistributions of flow and power that are not captured by traditional system codes. As a result, this methodology provides valuable reference data for benchmarking and underscores the importance of high-fidelity coupling in reactor safety analysis, especially when evaluating the reactor's response to severe transient scenarios.

Keywords: high-fidelity, neutronics CFD thermal hydraulics coupling, safety margins

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of multi-scale and multi-physics models for the simulation of light water reactors is becoming a generalized field of R&D in the industry. Aside the use of legacy industrial codes, it is part of the development of new “high fidelity” calculation methodologies (i.e., with reduced modeling biases) based on state-of-the-art methods [1][2], whose increasing use, made possible by the growth in high-performance computing capabilities, is enabling the establishment of calculation standards to support safety studies carried out using industrial codes, leading to a number of recent international benchmarking activities [3][4].

The current paper deals with a first coupling between a 3D neutronics FEM core code and a core/system Thermal hydraulics model at the CFD scale to simulate a stylized LW-SMR SLB transient.

Both codes were extensively validated on numerical and experimental data (Nuclear French fleet for the neutronics [6][7]) and dedicated PWR 3&4 loops 1/5 scale TH facilities on equilibrium/disequilibrium experiments for Fluent (but not publishable for IP reasons). The study evaluates the effectiveness of coupled neutronic and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations for a simplified KAIST reactor model [5] with a particular focus on both normal and accidental cooling

scenarios. A dedicated coupling interface between COCAGNE for neutronics and ANSYS Fluent 2024 R1 for CFD enables to simulate the reactor core and lower internals with detailed attention to mesh generation, boundary conditions, and post-processing. Two main configurations are investigated:

- a fully balanced configuration representative of normal reactor operation, in which all cold legs supply identical flow rates and temperatures.
- An unbalanced configuration simulating an accidental scenario representative of a steam line break (SLB), by introducing a higher (+30%) and colder flow in one cold leg, leading to strong flow asymmetry and turbulent mixing, as well as significant localized increases in core power.

The objective is to demonstrate the feasibility of such High-Fidelity coupling, in particular the impact of the CFD model throughout the system to properly generate flow heterogeneities in the core, leading to power instabilities. Preliminary results show a good numerical stability of the coupling, with manageable CPU times to model few seconds of the transient. Further work will be performed to benchmark these results against “industrial” calculation routes.

2. NUMERICAL MODELS

Both neutronics and Thermal hydraulics models are based on the small PWR stylized KAIST-1A core benchmark. It is a fictive 52 core PWR-like 17x17 assemblies surrounded by a standard reflector. The core contains 5 types of assemblies: - UOX-1: UOX assembly enriched at 2.0% ^{235}U . - UOX-2: UOX assembly enriched at 3.3% ^{235}U . - UOX-2 (BA-16): UOX assembly enriched at 3.3% ^{235}U and 16 gadolinia pins. - MOX-1: “tri-zone” (three Pu enrichment zones) MOX assembly with 8.7% enrichment in the central zone, 7.0% in the intermediate zone and 4.3% in the peripheral zone. - MOX-1 (BA-8): same as MOX-1 assembly with 8 gadolinia pins. The 900MW is modeled to work at 15% nominal power. The active height is 2m, without axial mixing grids. The core is reproduced on Fig 1.

2.1 Neutronics model

The neutronics core calculation scheme is based on a 2-step calculation based on Pij-MoC transport producing self-shielded multiparameter and homogenized cross sections, using CARABAS, a co-developed Framatome/EdF version of the APOLLO-2 lattice code embedded in an industrial GUI. The COCAGNE core code embarks a full 3D SPn flux solver. The code belongs to the new ODYSSEE calculation chain, extensively validated numerically and experimentally on the French NPP fleet [8]. Thermal transfer occurring between the coolant fluid and the fuel cladding is handled by the FRoST solver imbedded in the COCAGNE code. The neutronics calculations are performed using a SP1 approximation with few groups in energy. *Figure 1* (left part) reproduces the radial cross section of the core.

2.2 CFD model of the primary system

The objective of the CFD modeling is to capture the unsteady hydraulic phenomenon occurring in the Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) lower internals prior to core entry. To this end, a specific RPV lower internal model based on a typical Gen-III+ PWR has been geometrically scaled to match the KAIST core dimensions. *Figure 1* (right part) reproduces the TH model with the Cold Legs (CLs), the annular space, the lower plenum, the core and the outlet. To optimize computational efficiency, a full porous representation of the 52 fuel assemblies is employed to generate representative head losses within the

Lower Core Plate (LCP) and the core, both axially and transversely. No mixing grids are reproduced. So, no associated transverse blocking is considered in the transient, except in the bottom nozzle. The boundary conditions encompass 4 separate velocity inlets, and one pressure outlet. The computational mesh is generated using ANSYS Meshing Tool with unstructured methods, resulting in approximately 31 million predominantly tetrahedral cells, optimized consistently with sensitivity studies made during the interpretation of dedicated in 1/5 mockup experiments at Framatome Le Creusot.

Fluent solves (in transient mode) the energy equation with a Turbulence model based on Scale Adaptive Simulation (SAS). The Spatial discretization scheme is a second order upwind for momentum equation and energy with a first Order Upwind for Turbulent Kinetic Energy and Turbulent Dissipation Rate. Pressure Velocity coupling is based on Fractional Step method, as the Temporal discretization scheme is a non-iterative time advancement with a First Order Implicit formulation. The fluid properties are defined at a pressure of 155 bars. The corresponding density, viscosity, thermal capacity and conductivity are implemented using a User-Defined Function, interfacing with an external library to ensure accurate fluid property evaluation.

Figure 1 KAIST radial cross-section (left) / RPV internals Side & top views

2.3 Coupling methodology

The coupling between the COCAGNE and FLUENT solvers is classified as a weak coupling. In this approach, each solver independently resolves the equations governing its respective physical domains. The interaction between the two codes is managed through the exchange of interface data, as illustrated in Figure 2. These data are incorporated either as source terms - on the thermohydraulic solver side, where the fuel assembly power is injected into the coolant - or as boundary conditions - on the neutronic side, where parameters such as pressure, enthalpy, and velocity are applied to the fuel cladding.

Figure 2 Coupling scheme – data flux

The neutronic and CFD models utilize fundamentally different approaches to represent the reactor core, resulting in meshes that differ significantly in both type and cell volume. Hence, a dedicated data projection step is required. These data fluxes are supervised via a dedicated Python interface.

3. RESULTS ON A STEAM LINE BREAK TRANSIENT

3.1 Fully Balanced configuration

In this configuration, the fluid flow is expected to be symmetrical, as the coolant enters from each cold leg with identical velocities and temperature. Each incoming stream impinges on the core barrel and remains confined within its quarter of the annular space. The flow then proceeds directly downward through the downcomer before reaching the lower plenum. Within the lower plenum, the flow is damped to the lower head wall before its turnaround to pass through the FDD and distributes prior to entering the LCP. A slight gyration with respect to the RPV symmetry is observed in the lower plenum due to loop parity effect. This flow gyration is confirmed with the analysis of the mean velocity field. A minor discrepancy appears at the entrance of the lower plenum on CL4 side, where the velocity is noticeably reduced (see *Figure 3*) again attributable to loop's parity effect.

Figure 3 Scalar mean flow fields in the RPV – perpendicular to CL1 (left) and to CL2 (right) – below LCP (bottom)

During the initial iterations, the CFD fields differ from those of neutronics, resulting in a minor power transient. The power drops by approximately 6% (8 MW out of 135 MW) before returning to its expected value of 135 MW. Each core quarter seems to follow the same temporal evolution as shown in *Figure 4*.

Figure 4 Thermal core power evolution

Overall, these results are consistent with expectations; demonstrating that the thermal power exchanged between the codes remains stable.

3.2 Unbalanced configuration

In the unbalanced configuration, the fluid flow enters CL1 with a significantly higher velocity and lower temperature, resulting in approximately 75% more kinetic energy compared to other CLs. Consequently, the other flow pattern is highly asymmetrical and predominantly influenced by this incoming flow. As illustrated in *Figure 5*, the jet from CL1 impinges upon the core barrel, spreading laterally to occupy nearly half of the annular flow section. This strong inflow generates a turbulent structure in the lower plenum, characterized by a pair of counter-rotating swirls, which interact and mix the flows from CL2, CL3 and CL4. As a result, the CL1 flow dominates one half of the lower plenum, while the remaining CLs are confined in the other half.

Figure 5 Streamlines in the RPV – Top (Left) and Side (Right) views

The mean velocity fields corroborate streamlines analysis, revealing pronounced flow asymmetry between the vertical planes intersecting the CL pairs. Maximum velocities are observed in the plane crossing CL1, while greater heterogeneities are evident in the plane crossing CL2 (see *Figure 6*)

Figure 6 Scalar mean flow fields in the RPV – perpendicular to CL1 (left) and to CL2 (right) – below LCP (bottom)

Below the LCP, the velocity distribution is much heterogeneous than in the fully balanced configuration, with significantly higher velocities at the center and lower at the periphery. Additionally, beneath the FDD, the counter rotating swirls further disrupt the velocity field within the annular space, resulting in a backflow beneath the CL1 outlet. Within the core, the flow propagation directly influences the transport of thermal power. As shown in Figure 7, the power field is perturbed at $t=0.7s$, corresponding to the time required for the cold front to travel from CL1 to the LCP. Subsequently, both moderator density and thermal power exhibit turbulent behavior, with substantial fluctuations at the core center, resulting in pronounced power redistribution.

In line with Figure 7, the thermal power is notably disturbed, with the total core power increasing from 135 MW to 190 MW (a 50% rise) during the first second of the transient, mirroring the step change imposed by the boundary conditions (Figure 8). The core appears to split into two regions, the southern quarters; where the power is most pronounced, and the northern quarters where the power evolve gradually. The southern assemblies are directly exposed to the high-density flow traversing the LCP. After $t=3.0s$, the power disparity between the north and south regions diminishes, but a residual imbalanced of approximately 15% remains.

Figure 7 Density (Left) and Power (Right) fields between 0.0s and 4.0s of simulation

Figure 8 Thermal core power evolution – Whole Core (Top) Core Quarter (Bottom)

Overall, these results highlight the potential of using High-Fidelity coupling methodology for increased safety simulation in actual steam line break scenarios, as the coupled CFD/neutronic approach captures the complex redistribution of power under highly asymmetric flow conditions.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the feasibility and value of high-fidelity coupled neutronic and CFD simulations tested on a simplified KAIST reactor model. By combining the advanced capabilities of COCAGNE 2.7 and ANSYS Fluent 2024 R1, integrated through a dedicated coupling procedure, the

work provides detailed insights into the reactor core's behavior under both normal and accidental cooling conditions. Even if these codes were separately extensively validated; this work is the first attempt to couple the codes and test their performances on a challenging transient. The results for the fully balanced configuration confirm the stability and convergence of the coupling approach, with flow and power distributions aligning with expected reactor physics for normal operation. In contrast, the unbalanced configuration, designed to emulate a severe cooling asymmetry, reveals significant flow and power redistribution within the core. The coupled simulation captures the emergence of strong asymmetries, turbulent structures, and transient power increases, all of which are critical for assessing safety margins during challenging scenarios such as a steam line break. The study highlights the potential of coupled CFD/neutronic modeling to provide high-quality reference data for benchmarking and to enhance the understanding of complex reactor transients. These findings support the continued development and application of such advanced simulation tools for reactor safety analysis and design optimization. Further work will be performed to benchmark these results against "industrial" calculation routes to pinpoint differences on safety quantities such as critical heat flux location, as well as peaking factors. This approach will be extended soon to other transients requiring high-fidelity approaches. It should also benefit from the forthcoming AMETIST project [9], launched as a new Euratom call in September 2026

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